

**THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP ON
ORGANIZATIONAL AGILITY: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF
IMPROVISATIONAL BEHAVIOR IN THE BUSINESS PROCESS
OUTSOURCING INDUSTRY**

Mulazim Abbas

University Institute of Management Sciences, PMAS-AAUR Rawalpindi,
Pakistan, MS Management Sciences scholar mulazimabbas123@gmail.com

Osman Zulfiqar Alvi

University Institute of Management Sciences, PMAS-AAUR Rawalpindi,
Pakistan, Supervisor osman.z.alvi@gmail.com

Pakiza Ashraf

University Institute of Management Sciences, PMAS-AAUR Rawalpindi,
Pakistan, MS Management Sciences scholar apakiza74@gmail.com

Abstract

This research investigates the mediating role of improvisational behaviour (IB) in the relationship between strategic entrepreneurship (SE) and organizational agility (OA) within Pakistan's BPO sector. It emphasizes that while SE characterized by entrepreneurial mindset, innovation, and resource reconfiguration positively influences OA, the presence of IB enhances this relationship. The study proposes that employees' ability to act spontaneously and adaptively strengthens the impact of SE on OA. Empirical findings from BPO firms in Islamabad and Rawalpindi, analysed using PLS-SEM, reveal that SE significantly boosts IB, which in turn positively affects OA. Furthermore, IB partially mediates this relationship, suggesting that agility is not solely the result of strategic intent but also hinges on employees' flexible, real-time actions. This highlights IB as a crucial behavioural mechanism that bridges SE and OA, adding depth to the theoretical model and offering actionable insights for firms operating in dynamic service environments.

Keywords: Strategic Entrepreneurship, Organizational Agility, Improvisational Behavior, Business Process Outsourcing, Competitive Advantage

Introduction

Firms are interested in attaining high level of competitiveness and organizational performance because of a dynamic business environment. The frequency of changing customer demands is increasing today (Vinodh et al., 2010b), whereas the change in the environment is becoming faster (Ahlback et al., 2017). This improves the market dynamics as well as the risk level (Vinodh et al., 2010b) and thus increases the level of competition (Vinodh, 2010). Some of the organizational capabilities exist that may help in providing adequate and efficient response of the firm to constantly changing environmental situations and utilizing such changes to the advantage of the business. In this regard, Hatzijordanou et al., (2019) noted that agility attains great heights that are useful in the generation of business profits amicably. Also, Meinhardt et al., (2018) corroborated the high effect on business environment dynamism and recommended agility as a source of competitive advantage. The use of the concept of agility in a business context was first established in 1982, where it was identified to mean the, ability to respond speedily, to the changing conditions (Brown & Agnew, 1982). The original source (Brown & Agnew, 1982) is quite rarely mentioned; however, the concept of agility is still applicable: Organization agility can be understood as the ability of an organization to maintain and expand itself within the climate of uncertainty and flux in business (Vinodh et al., 2012a). Most scholars agree that Organizational Agility began with the Iacocca Institute's 1991 Lehigh Report that was tasked with examining causes and solutions for slow economic expansion of the U.S. manufacturing sector. The concept of agility must be firmly anchored in management theory (Yusuf et al., 1999). In the early 1990s, a new strategy for coping with dynamic and turbulent environments emerged: agility. Agile Manufacturing can be defined as the capability of organizations to continuously adapt and sustain in a competitive environment that is characterized by fluctuating and unpredictable market conditions with products and services that are defined by the consumer (Gunasekaran, 1999).

Initially, agility was a new concept in contemporary administrative thought. Another author described agility as the capacity for flexible movement within the organization (Sherehiy, 2008). Agility refers to the ability to cope with high and unpredictable volatility and fluctuation in profitability (Erande and Verma, 2008).

Strategic entrepreneurship is undoubtedly grounded in change; innovation involves advancing to new levels (Kuratko & Audretsch 2009). The original literature on strategic entrepreneurship, along with contemporary bibliometric analyses, demonstrates that SE captures the synergy and interdependence between entrepreneurship and strategic management (Hitt et al., 2001). It evolved from the field of economics (Knight, 1921; Schumpeter, 1942) and later from the field of management. Kuratko and Morris (2018) defined strategic entrepreneurship (SE) as a wide range of entrepreneurial initiatives or development activities in an organization's efforts towards achieving strategic positioning and superior competitive advantage. It has been defined as a process of striving for a higher level of performance and a hybrid of gradual and radical improvements, as well as a combination of strategic and enterprising behaviours (Hitt et al., 2001; Ketchen 2007). In addition, strategic entrepreneurship has been defined as "a specific type of strategy in which a firm know that sustainable competitive advantage does not depend on any specific competency; rather, competitive advantage is contingent on the firm's capability to sustain innovation over time to outcompete other firms" (Webb et al. 2010). Despite an increasing attention from the scholars, and the recognition that there is much value in the integration of strategy and entrepreneurship, the concept of strategic entrepreneurship is still rather ill-defined and under-theorized (Mazzei et al., 2017; Simsek et al., 2017; Imran et al.2023).

The topic of nature of SE is in debate almost 20 years. According to Ireland et al. (2003), SE is a combination of processes in which individuals and organisations actively pursue opportunities and ensuing benefits and a

combination of the entrepreneurial culture, leaders and spirit. According to Morris et al. (2008), SEs can be defined as all organizational relevance innovation which takes place in a firm but does not result in an establishment of new business enterprise.

Innovation is essential for the survival of organizations (Amabile 1988). Improvisational behaviour as the foundation to the complex social processes of knowledge, creation and decision making has been claimed to be a way to comprehend and embark on innovation as firms seek accelerated cycle times and more profound solutions (Khattak et al. 2022; Crossan 1997a). Thus, the role of improvisational behaviour in the innovation processes like the new product development for instance has been getting significant attention (for example, Eisenhardt & Tabrizi, 1995; Moorman & Miner, 1998; Kamoche & Cunha, 2001). According to Brown and Eisenhardt (1998, p. 33), 'improvisational behaviour allows managers to keep on adapting with change and to constantly innovate and deliver products and services to the market,' is considered by Poolton and Ismail (2000) as one of the areas of new innovations. The theory of improvisational behaviour is mostly derived from observations made with reference to jazz and theatre improvisation (for example, Organization Science's Special Issue on Jazz Improvisation 1998).

The concept of outsourcing is not novel to the society today. The earliest evidence for outsourcing could perhaps be traced back to the early Industrial Revolution in the 1700s when manufacturers began moving the manufactured goods to other countries with cheaper labour, following the principles of Adam Smith in his book, 'The Wealth of Nations'. The business processing outsourcing (BPO) industry is increasingly growing in Asia and thus can be considered as one of the growing industries in the world. In other words, the BPO industry mainly consists of outsourcing back-office operations, support services and call centres, which are less expensive and more efficient to be operated internationally and offer superior service than domestic country. The majority of the call centres are the customer service divisions of

English-speaking banks, retail firms, insurance companies, travel agents, computer support, and telephone sales. Until recently this industry was located in USA, UK and Australia. India the industry leader is followed by Canada. These market leaders are followed by China, Mexico, and Central Eastern Europe and few other countries (Cu, 2006).

Hence, the concept of strategic entrepreneurship has immense importance in the case of BPO industry where the ability to transform the business entity is imperative. Due to rapid advancement in technology as well as evolving client needs, BPO firms must be innovative to remain sustainable in this complex environment. Through strategic entrepreneurship, these firms are able to identify new opportunities and at the same time increase their resource utilization efficiency for competitiveness and increased firm agility. The concept of organizational agility is especially relevant for the BPO industry because it allows firms to respond to such important factors as technological changes, new market demands, and service delivery in different geographical locations quickly and sustainably protect and build the competitive advantage and operating performance. Also, it considers that improvisational behaviour mediates this relationship because it enables BPO firms to adapt to various challenges and opportunities. Many distinct strategies occur due to the changeability of the clients that the BPO industry undertake and the fluctuating market conditions. Promoting the culture of improvisational behavior may be another factor that will help BPO firms to strengthen the organizational agility as a characteristic of their work.

Literature Review

Dynamic capabilities, as described by Teece (2007), are essentially the potential of firms to exchange and be extra progressive because of pressure and/or unpredictability elements. Using DC theory, this study will be capable of examine how SE supports organizational agility through constructing and deploying dynamic capabilities that permit firms to perform swiftly in dynamic environments. One can identify improvisational behavior as another

form of outcomes of dynamic capabilities especially in high turbulence. Li and Liu (2014) have noted that improvisational capabilities are related to dynamic capabilities since both concepts revolve around the notion of ‘instant creation’ as well as the ability to adapt quickly. This view is supported by Zhang et al. (2023) who place improvisational abilities in the evolution of dynamic capabilities. DC Theory enables this study to assess the mediating role of improvisational behaviour in relation to SE and OA to explain how dynamic capabilities may positively impact agility during unexpected conditions. Dynamic Capabilities Theory is a strong foundation to analyse the relationship between Strategic Entrepreneurship, Organizational Agility, and Improvisational Behavior. It provides insights on how firms can create and use dynamic capabilities for the purpose of creating, maintaining and enhancing their competitiveness (Winter ,2003). The Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) Theory was developed by Miller (1983) and later extended by Lumpkin and Dess (1996) giving a conceptual backdrop to gauge the strategic direction of firms operating under entrepreneurial settings. EO Theory identifies some important dimensions such as innovation, risk taking propensity, and pro-action which is essential for the firms that want to engage in new ventures and control risks and set their environment. It is most closely related to the concept of strategic entrepreneurship involving the application of entrepreneurship at the firm level to create a competitive advantage and to foster dynamic capabilities.

High EO firms are more committed to adapting and adjusting their strategic actions to changing environments so that the innovative and proactive nature of the firms allows them to effectively manage market forces and stay ahead. The second antecedent is the improvisational behaviour that is related to the EO dimensions, which is also highly significant because it enables firms to successfully deal with emergent environmental conditions, being a mediator between strategic entrepreneurship and organisational agility. Research by Lumpkin and Dess (1996) and Wiklund & Shepherd (2005)

shows that Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) is still important. Their research shows that companies with high Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) are generally more agile and do better overall. Thus, EO Theory can be considered strong theoretical support for studies on strategic entrepreneurship's effects on organizational agility, focusing on innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness with theoretical support for the role of improvisational behaviour. On the basis of definitions given across various sources, agility can be defined in terms of speed, the ability to respond to the requirements quickly, group work as well as a common goal in an organization. In more specific terms, it is understood as the speed and appropriate reaction of a well-coordinated team to achieve an aim within the context of certain alterations in their environment (Yeganegi and Azar, 2012, p. 517).

Organizational Agility

Organizational agility can be defined as the organization's capability to respond quickly and proactively to change and to deliver, a priori, organizational solutions to what might become needs (Nelson & Harvey, 1995, p. 16). OA also provides the capability to thrive and evolve in an unpredicted competitive structure of the continual change by responding quickly to new markets and addressing the demands and wants of customers in terms of products and services (Gunasekaran, 1999; Hussain et al. 2011). OA is the effective deployment of competition rules which include speed, flexibility, innovation, and quality in integrating resources and restructuring best practices in a technical knowledge environment leading to offering services or products that satisfy the clients in a dynamic environment (Yusuf et al., 1999). It is about how the organisation is capable to operate satisfactorily within a rapidly and constantly shifting and unstructured global market place, delivering high standard and successful performance (Tsourveloudis & Valavanis, 2002). Further, OA allows an organisation to complete certain tasks efficiently and control the opportunities and threats in business processes (Ardichvile et al., 2003). The concept of OA derives from the

performance characteristics of an agile organization and is rooted in two related concepts: Structural characteristics that have been closely associated with “organizational adaptability” and “organizational flexibility. Organizational flexibility refers to quick adaptation of organizational form and structure, coupled with a lesser formalization in its business environment (Sherehiy et al., 2007). OA consists of several key elements: As identified by Sherehiy (2008) they are (1) speed and flexibility, (2) analysing changes of the environment, (3) high quality of produced goods, (4) the accuracy of information included in products and services, (5) interactions with social issues and environment, (6) single technologies collecting, and (7) internal interactions within institutions and between them. OA is a set of ideas for constant enhancement, reduction in organizational hierarchies, work groups, reduction in waste, and rational utilisation of resources, and control over preparation chain. According to David (2009), Japanese companies have integrated a system that is known as OA with an aim of cutting on their expenditures through the elimination of any unnecessary expenses. OA is constructed of three basic elements: Of these, there are three that are strategic: (1) sensing agility, (2) decision-making, and (3) acting using agility and its application (Pavlou and El Sawy 2010). Park (2011) defined three dimensions of OA as follows: sensing agility, decision-making agility and acting agility.

Sensing agility can defined as the organizational ability to and monitor the activity and changes occurring in the external environment (for instance, the change in customer preferences; the emergence of new competitors; new technologies) in the timely manner (Rehman et al. 2021; Park, 2011). (It consists of a conscious observation of environmental activities that may affect organizational strategy, competitive work and future performance, gaining information associated with alterations in the environment, and discarding nonessential data according to certain principles and frameworks laid down (El-Sawy, 1985). This task is associated with decision and implementation (Daft & Weick, 1984; Dutton & Duncan, 1987) and concerns the processes of

organisational responsiveness to environmental stimuli (Smircich & Stubbart, 1985). This involves gathering and stockpiling information from different sources, reorganising it and assessing it to give interpretations of events to explain business consequences as they happen, and to show opportunities and threats. It has strategizing to work out how the allocation and mobilisation of resources and new competitive responses are going to be managed. Decision-making comprises of several activities and is intended to ensure that the maximum opportunity is gained from surrounding environment and the impact of threats in the environment is eliminated (Thomas et al., 1993, Houghton et al., 2004). Being agile entails reconfiguration of organisational assets and alteration of business processes consistent with the theories on decision making to respond to changes in the environment. It is possible for an organisation to change business processes within an organisation by different procedures and resources including restructuring of the organisational structure (Dutton & Duncan, 1987; Thomas et al., 1993). By definition, organizational agility cuts across the production department in all the enterprise departments., as underlined by Arteta & Giachetti (2004), agility means organisational capability that consists not only of response-ability, but also knowledge management. OA intervenes with a firm's dynamic capabilities that function as screening mechanisms for unforeseen change in market or industry (Nejatian et al., 2018). What this means is that; firms may be able to have Organizational Agility in as much as it pertains to the internal structural and process formulation, use of System and recognition of standards within the industry (Harraf et.al., 2015).

OA as a concept also includes the following sub-concepts: agile enterprise, agile workers, agile supply chain, agile customers and agile services (Breu et al., 2012; Zainal et al., 2020). The OA has been approached from workforce perspective such as, workforce agility (Patil & Suresh, 2019), managerial OA perspective (management agility) (Bugarová & Šimíčková, 2019), production OA perspective (manufacturing agility) (Schuh, Prote,

Gützlaff, Ays, & Donner, 2019), and marketing OA perspective (Khan, 2020). Firms leverage on OA to capture flexibility, speed, cost, as well as absorptive capacity. Yang and Liu (2012) identified four dimensions of OA: customer relationship, enrichment-synergy competition and cooperation, another is ability to manage the organization within his / her environment changes, and lastly ability to manage people through information sharing. In the same context, the Zhang and Sharifi (2000) noted that that the agility drivers mean changes in the environment that compel businesses to maintain competitiveness.

Strategic Entrepreneurship

Covin and Kuratko (2008) consider SE in the terms of corporate entrepreneurship. In their analysis, while SE encompasses a vast spectrum of entrepreneurship, it is not necessarily associated with new organisations being established in the corporation. However, they all are associated either with large-scale or otherwise organisationally significant innovations implemented in the pursuit of competitive benefit. Unlike the concept of corporate venturing, where the company gets involved in the establishment of other new organizations, SE entails a wide range of entrepreneurial actions, which includes setting up new organizations as a part of the firm. All forms of SE have one thing in common: They entail display of organizationally significant changes that are implemented in the quest for competitive advantage. SE describes opportunity-seeking and advantage-seeking activities that take place at the same time (Ireland et al., 2003). Since SE has begun attracting more attention from researchers, several models have been proposed to the literature. The most extensively acknowledged and adopted model of SE (Ireland et al., 2003) identifies four key elements: They include the following: (1) entrepreneurship culture, mindset, and leadership; (2) resource management for strategic innovation; (3) creativity, and (4) developing radical and incremental innovation as a crucial factor in the creation of competitive advantage. SE is defined as a combination of venturing

(opportunity-seeking) and domination (strategic) activities aimed at generating value (Hitt et al., 2001). It includes all innovations organizationally relevant at any level and throughout all aspects of the firm for exploitation and exploration (Kuratko; Audretsch, 2013). Such activity is crucial to make products or services unique from other competitors and to ensure greater benefits to the customers (Hoskisson et al., 2013), and is the basic process for growth, existence, competition and profitability (Ireland et al., 2001).

Strategic Entrepreneurship is analysed as the actions distinctively entrepreneurial (concerning opportunity) intertwined with actions more appropriately labelled strategic (seeking advantage). This concept can be regarded as one of the modes of the strategic entrepreneurship being a way of strategy making associated with the capability of making timely decisions in a shifting environment (Bird, 1988). In particular, Mintzberg and Waters (1982) described entrepreneurial strategic decision-making in terms of its level of planning and clear vision with the inherent capacity to alter that vision. Bird (1988) also supports the notion of vision in SE as he notes that when a firm has its eyes set on the present, it means that it has a vision concerning the future. On the other hand, Eisenhardt et al. (2000) talk of flexibility under managing the chaos of change and outline six generic processes for mainstreaming entrepreneurship as a strategic process. These include improvisation, co-adaptation, patching, regeneration, experimenting and time pacing. Eisenhardt et al.'s (2000) six-process framework is similar to the six domains of SE identified by Ireland et al. (2001): new product or service development, access to resources (networks), globalization, knowledge transfer and development, increase in firm size and scope, selection and execution of strategies by top management teams and boards. Hitt et al. (2001) changed these domains to external networks, resources and organizational learning, innovation and internationalization when they both extend and refined SE as a research discipline and a concept. These two views emphasis on networks, learning and growth, however, the view advanced by Hitt et al.

(2001) in their revised vision focuses more on resources, competencies, and capabilities that can help in the creation of sustainable competitive advantage during enterprise behavior. Opportunity identification in the literature on SE is postulated to be a source of competitive advantage (Ullah et al. 2018; Hitt et al., 2002), which may entail entrepreneurial opportunity creation while laying the foundations for its exploitation (Zahra, 2008). This paper and previous bibliometric works reveals that SE captures the complementary relationship that exists between entrepreneurship and strategic management as embraced by the founding works of SE as well as current literature (Hitt et al., 2002). The origin of SE can be traced to the discipline of economics or Knight (1921) and Schumpeter (1942) and management.

Improvisational Behaviour

Moorman and Miner (1998a) try to describe the concept of improvisational behaviour as the deliberate creation and performance of unrehearsed action. People are not limited to performing novelty routines at any specific time, but based on the signal to solve a particular problem, engage in an improvisational behaviour which is an opportunity that has no planned script. Baker et al. (2003) define that one can use improvisation in order to figure out how the available resources can support the existing objectives (causation), or to explore what can be achieved (effectuation). While only recently has research attention been directed to improvisational behaviour in the context of entrepreneurship (e.g., Baker et al., 2003; Baker & Nelson, 2005; Hmieleski & Corbett, 2006), there has been several valuable examinations of the concept of improvisational behaviour in the context of large-form organizations. A lot of works that have been done in the past have highlighted the relationship between improvisational behaviour and new product development. For example, Eisenhardt and Tabrizi's (1995) empirical comparison of rational versus emergent process of new product development argues that real-time and operational approach to product development is better than more rational and system-oriented approach. In their subsequent study, Moorman and

Miner (1998b) identified three structural contingents of improvisation, namely environmental turbulence, organizational memory systems and real-time information systems. Miner, Bassoff, and Moorman (2001) noted that improvisational behaviour can be legitimated and integrated into more regular, structured organizational activities and some authors claimed that firms might plan for improvisational behaviour. Other works on improvisational behaviour have discussed its connection to change, leadership and change management and innovation and learning. Brown and Eisenhardt (1997) discussed exploration of continuous change processes in forty large technology-based companies and concluded that the companies who are more excellent changer are capable to improvise more. Likewise, Orlikowski (1996) and Cunha and Cunha (2003) demonstrated that organizational change can work well with improvisational behaviour. A study by Cunha, Kamoche, and Cunha (2003) revealed three major antecedents of improvisational leadership:

The three important factors include perimeter; the level of environmental turbulence experienced by the group, prominence; the significance of the event to the leader and usability; the ease of use of resources in the event. Similarly, analysing the unsuccessful experience of commercialisation, Garud and Karnoe (2003) defined improvisation-type strategies as being more effective than derived-from-plan strategies that were aimed at creating new technologies. The study by Vera and Crosson (2005) revealed that organizational culture and real-time information are positive mechanisms through which the relationship between improvisational behaviour and innovation occurs. In the studies of these scholars, there was no evidence of a main effect of improvisational behaviour on innovation, implying that improvisational behaviour is positive or negative. Furthermore, they realized that training programs can be established for the improvement of improvisational behaviour. Thus, a number of important conclusions regarding the relevance of the studies and entrepreneurship in general can be made. First, based on the research findings it can be concluded that

improvisational behaviour appears to be a promising behavioral approach to the management of change, and particularly in the context of dynamic environment that newly established ventures operating in rapidly growing industries experience. Another recent empirical research by Hmieleski and Ensley (2004) points out that those entrepreneurs, the so-called ‘improvisers’ achieve higher performance compared to their counterparts who are not inclined to improvising in the conditions of highly uncertain industrial environments of startups. Second, improvisational activities can be inserted into certain tasks in a workplace and into organizational culture. Therefore, it might be useful for entrepreneurs to actively manage the level of improvisational behaviour in their organizations with reference to the demands in the environment. Third, it did not mean that improvisational behaviour was beneficial under all conditions, while the beneficial effects of improvisational behaviour were contingent on certain factors. Last, but not the least, people can also be taught how to improvise. Thus, studying the improvisational behavior of entrepreneurs could be useful to improve the curriculum for training new entrepreneurs, which in turn might enhance the rates of survival and growth of new ventures. Considering the centrality of improvisational behaviour within the entrepreneurial process, further and more in-depth empirical investigations of entrepreneurial improvisational behavior may lead to a greater understanding of the central research question of entrepreneurship: how opportunities for future goods and services are identified, selected and created (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Venkataraman, 1997).

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Materials And Methods

In the present study, the quantitative research design was used. Different data collection tools were incorporated to test hypotheses and answer the research questions of the study. Furthermore, the researcher selected a cross-sectional approach rather than a longitudinal study. Cross-sectional approach was selected on the basis of cost and time consideration. The research philosophy employed in this study was positivism. Positivism emphasizes that observation and measurement of events in a scientific manner yield valid knowledge (Bryman, 2016). It supports the idea that reality exists independently and can be observed and analysed without personal biases interfering (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009)

For this study, the researcher employed a deductive approach. As noted by Robson (2011), the deductive approach is well-suited for analysing the validity of theoretical propositions using quantitative data. There are several methods that can be used in research depending on the type of investigation or research questions that have been set. Some of the general research approaches include experiments, case studies, ethnographic, grounded theory, and surveys. This research, therefore, adopted the survey research method and employed the use of questionnaires as the data collection instruments.

The survey method was most suitable for this research because it allowed the collection of a significant amount of data from a large population within a short period of time (Creswell, 2009). The unit of analysis was one of the most important concepts in designing the research study, as it defined the main object under consideration and analysis. In research, there are various types of units of analysis that can be used, and they include individuals, groups, organizations, and social artifacts. For this study, the unit of analysis was CSR (Customer Service Representative) of the BPO industry. The target population for this study consisted of BPO industries located in the twin cities (Islamabad and Rawalpindi). The sampling method was a technique of choosing a part of the target population for a study. There are two main categories of sampling techniques: namely, probability sampling and non-probability sampling. In this study, the author considered convenience sampling as the research technique for this study, which was a non-probability sampling technique. It entailed choosing CSRs who were willing to join and were easily accessible. This strategy is realistic and economical. The sample size for this research was estimated with the help of the 15:1 ratio, which is suggested by Hair et al. (2018).

The total number of items was 31; thus, a minimum of 465 respondents was required for the study. The data for this study was collected with the help of a structured questionnaire. It employed a 5-point Likert scale in order to capture the responses, which ranged from 'Strongly Disagree' to 'Strongly Agree.' The items were taken from previous studies to maintain the reliability and validity of the study. The items used to measure Strategic Entrepreneurship were sourced from Siren et al. (2012). Organizational agility items were adopted from Lee et al. (2015), while the improvisational behaviour items were sourced from Vera & Crossan (2005). Hence, using structured quantitative questionnaires with standardised indices and items made the collected data credible, as well as pertinent to the research aims and

objectives. The data collected from the questionnaires was analysed using SPSS and Smart PLS.

Data Analysis And Results

The data collected from the questionnaires was analysed using SPSS and Smart PLS. For demographics, there was a use of SPSS. In the case of complex models with multiple constructs and indicators, the application of Smart PLS is recommended, especially when the research purposes are focused on the testing of theoretical models and hypotheses, due to the high flexibility and predictive accuracy of SEM in this method (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics, highlighting the skewness and kurtosis values of the study variables to assess the normality of the data. According to Hair et al. (2017), acceptable skewness and kurtosis values range from -1 to +1, indicating a near-normal distribution. In this study, Strategic Entrepreneurship (Skewness = 0.022; Kurtosis = -0.251), Organizational Agility (Skewness = 0.116; Kurtosis = -0.395), and Improvisational Behavior (Skewness = 0.119; Kurtosis = -0.285) all fall within the acceptable range, suggesting that the data are approximately normally distributed. This confirms the suitability of applying parametric statistical analyses such as regression and hypothesis testing.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

				Std.				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	
SE	517	1.50	5.00	3.4953	.58936	.022	.107	-.251 .214
OA	517	1.00	3.75	2.1623	.55846	.116	.107	-.395 .214
IB	517	1.00	3.57	2.1163	.53245	.119	.107	-.285 .214

Source: Author's Estimation

Convergent validity is the degree to which various measures of the same construct are correlated and actually measure the concept of interest. It makes sure that the observed variables which are theoretically connected to the same

latent construct do correlate with each other. The following are some of the important statistical measures used to determine this form of validity; Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Composite Reliability (CR), factor loadings, and internal consistency reliability. Cronbach Alpha is a commonly adopted measure of internal consistency and reliability of a scale or questionnaire. Hair et al. (2017) state that Cronbach's Alpha must be between 0.70 and 0.95. This study satisfies that requirement, as Cronbach Alpha of Improvisational Behavior is 0.913, Organizational Agility is 0.954, and Strategic Entrepreneurship is 0.958. The Composite Reliability (CR) values in this study are 0.931, 0.960, and 0.963 which are well above the recommended value. Hair et al. (2017) state that to prove convergent validity, the AVE must be 0.50 or more. The AVE values in this study are 0.658, 0.664 and 0.685. According to Hair et al. (2017), factor loadings should exceed 0.50. In this study, all indicators surpassed this benchmark. These strong loadings confirm that the measurement items effectively capture the intended constructs. These results confirm the reliability and convergent validity of the constructs used in this study on Strategic Entrepreneurship, Organizational Agility, and Improvisational Behavior.

Table 2: Model

ITEMS	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
IMPRO1	0.821	0.913	0.931	0.658
IMPRO2	0.792			
IMPRO3	0.830			
IMPRO4	0.805			
IMPRO5	0.801			
IMPRO6	0.819			
IMPRO7	0.809			
OA1	0.803	0.954	0.960	0.664
OA2	0.812			

OA3	0.835			
OA4	0.805			
OA5	0.794			
OA6	0.806			
OA7	0.822			
OA8	0.822			
OA9	0.822			
OA10	0.821			
OA11	0.826			
OA12	0.810			
SE1	0.826	0.958	0.963	0.685
SE2	0.815			
SE2	0.828			
SE4	0.835			
SE5	0.830			
SE6	0.841			
SE7	0.838			
SE8	0.833			
SE9	0.839			
SE10	0.815			
SE11	0.816			
SE12	0.814			

Source: Author's Estimation

Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis testing on SmartPLS by bootstrapping indicated that there were direct and indirect relations between the constructs, which were significant at a statistical level. Particularly, all the three direct hypotheses were admitted: improvising behaviours had a significant influence on organizational agility (beta coefficient= 0.484, t =11.969, p= 0.000), strategic

entrepreneurship had a significant effect on improvising behaviours (beta coefficient = 0.618, $t = 23.547$, $p = 0.000$) and strategic entrepreneurship directly influenced organizational agility (beta coefficient = 0.236, $t = 5.610$, $p = 0.00$). Such results show that entrepreneurial practice and employee improvisation are strategically relevant in improving agility, especially in the vibrant BPO industry of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Besides, mediation analysis showed that the relationship between Strategic Entrepreneurship and Organizational Agility is partially mediated by Improvisational Behaviour, as the indirect effect is significant ($\beta = 0.299$, $t = 10.448$, $p = 0.000$), and therefore Strategic Entrepreneurship has both a direct and indirect positive effect on agility through the development of the improvisational abilities of the employees.

Table 3: Direct Relationship-Path Coefficient.

Constructs	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Accepted/Rejected
Improvisational Behaviour -> Organizational Agility	0.484	0.484	0.040	11.969	0.000	Accepted
Strategic Entrepreneurship -> Improvisational Behaviour	0.618	0.619	0.026	23.547	0.000	Accepted
Strategic Entrepreneurship -> Organizational Agility	0.236	0.236	0.042	5.610	0.000	Accepted

Source: Author's Estimation

Table 4: Indirect Effect -Mediation Effect

Constructs	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Type of Mediation
Strategic Entrepreneurship - >Improvisational Behaviour -> Organizational Agility	0.299	0.300	0.029	10.448	0.000	Partial Mediation

Source: Author's Estimation

Discussion

The study was able to fulfil all four of its research objectives by empirically verifying the relationships of SE-IB-OA in the Pakistan BPO sector. The first objective was achieved when a substantial positive effect was established between SE and OA, meaning that entrepreneurial approaches allow firms to be more adaptable and responsive, corresponding to the Dynamic Capabilities View (Teece, 2007, 2012). The second objective indicated that SE strongly enhances IB, confirming the Entrepreneurial Orientation paradigm that associates risk-taking, autonomy, and proactiveness to adaptability in behaviours (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996; Rhee et al., 2010). The third objective indicated that IB is a strong integrator of OA, and the concept of behaviour flexibility and real-time decision-making are crucial to establishing agility (Cegarra-Navarro et al., 2016; Leybourne, 2006). Finally, the fourth objective established that IB partially mediates SE-OA relationship and strengthened the fact that improvisation is a critical behavioural mechanism that transforms strategic intent into agility (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). Its

results provide not only theoretical contribution to linking SE and IB to the paradigm of dynamic capabilities but also highlight the practicality of enhancing employee empowerment and instilling entrepreneurial mindset in the culture of agility in highly dynamic service world, particularly within culturally hierarchical settings such as Pakistan.

Conclusion

This study contributes both theoretically and practically to the understanding of how Strategic Entrepreneurship (SE), Improvisational Behaviour (IB), and Organizational Agility (OA) interact in dynamic service settings, particularly within Pakistan's BPO sector. Theoretically, it extends the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece et al., 1997) by recognizing improvisation not merely as a reactive trait but as a strategic dynamic capability that enables real-time translation of entrepreneurial intent into agile outcomes (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). By empirically validating IB as a partial mediator between SE and OA, the study proposes a novel behavioural mechanism relevant for underdeveloped systems in emerging markets. It also contextualizes existing Western-centric models within the cultural and structural realities of Pakistan's service economy (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). Practically, the findings emphasize the importance of empowering frontline employees, embedding strategic entrepreneurship across all organizational levels, and promoting improvisation to enhance agility—crucial for BPO firms competing in rapidly changing client environments. Policymakers and regulators are urged to support this behavioural shift by offering training and incentives for agility-driven strategies. However, limitations such as geographic confinement to Islamabad and Rawalpindi, a modest sample size, a cross-sectional design, and reliance on self-reported data restrict generalizability and causal inference. Future research should address these through longitudinal designs, cross-industry applications, and inclusion of moderators like leadership style and digital maturity. In conclusion, this study confirms that strategic entrepreneurship directly and indirectly fosters organizational agility through

improvisational behaviour, offering valuable insights for theory and actionable recommendations for practice in volatile service sectors.

References

- Ahlbäck, K., Fahrback, C., Murarka, M., & Salo, O. (2017). How to create an agile organization. *McKinsey & Company*.
- Amabile, T. M. (1988). A model of creativity and innovation in organizations. *Research in Organizational Behavior/JAI Press*.
- Ardichvile, A., Cardozo, R., & Ray, S. (2003). A theory of entrepreneurial opportunity identification and development. *Journal of Business Venturing, 18*(1), 105–123.
- Arteta, B. M., & Giachetti, R. E. (2004). A measure of agility as the complexity of the enterprise system. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing, 20*(6), 495–503.
- Baker, T., & Nelson, R. E. (2005). Creating something from nothing: Resource construction through entrepreneurial bricolage. *Administrative Science Quarterly, 50*(3), 329–366.
- Baker, T., Miner, A. S., & Easley, D. T. (2003). Improvising firms: Bricolage, account giving and improvisational competencies in the founding process. *Research Policy, 32*(2), 255–276.
- Breu, K., Hemingway, C. J., Strathern, M., & Bridger, D. (2012). Workforce agility: The new employee strategy for the knowledge economy. *Journal of Information Technology, 17*(1), 21–31.
- Brown, J. L., & Agnew, N. M. (1982). Corporate agility. *Business Horizons, 25*(2), 29–33.
- Brown, S. L., & Eisenhardt, K. M. (1997). The art of continuous change. *Administrative Science Quarterly, 42*(1), 1–34.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Buganová, K., & Šimíčková, J. (2019). Risk management in the context of managerial agility. *Transportation Research Procedia, 40*, 986–993.

- Cegarra-Navarro, J. G., Soto-Acosta, P., & Wensley, A. K. (2016). Structured knowledge processes and firm performance: The role of organizational agility. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), 1544–1549.
- Covin, J. G., Ireland, R. D., & Kuratko, D. F. (2003). The exploration and exploitation functions of corporate venturing. Paper presented at the Academy of Management meetings, Seattle, WA.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research designs: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*.
- Crossan, M. M. (1997). Improve to innovate. *Ivey Business Quarterly*, 62, 37–42.
- Cu, E. L. (2006). Philippine BPO industry: 2005 scorecard. Retrieved February 27, 2006, from
- Cunha, M. P. E., Kamoche, K., & Cunha, R. C. E. (2003). Organizational improvisation and leadership—a field study in two computer-mediated settings. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 33(1), 34–57.
- Daft, R. L., & Weick, K. E. (1984). Toward a model of organizations as interpretation systems. *Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), 284–295.
- David, F. R. (2009). *Strategic management: Concepts and cases* (12th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Dutton, J. E., & Duncan, R. B. (1987). The creation of momentum for change through the process of strategic issue diagnosis. *Strategic Management Journal*, 8(3), 279–295.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., & Martin, J. A. (2000). Dynamic capabilities: What are they? *Strategic Management Journal*, 21(10–11), 1105–1121.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., & Tabrizi, B. N. (1995). Accelerating adaptive processes: Product innovation in the global computer industry. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 84–110.

- El-Sawy, O. A. (1985). Personal information systems for strategic scanning in turbulent environments: Can harnessing chaos help? *MIS Quarterly*, 9(1), 17–29.
- Erande, A. S., & Verma, A. K. (2008). Measuring agility of organizations—a comprehensive agility measurement tool (CAMT). *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 6(3).
- Gunasekaran, A. (1999). Agile manufacturing: A framework for research and development. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62(1–2), 87–105.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Matthews, L. M., Matthews, R. L., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). PLS-SEM or CB-SEM: Updated guidelines on which method to use. *International Journal of Multivariate Data Analysis*, 1(2), 107–123.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Gudergan, S. P. (2018). *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage.
- Harraf, A., Wanasika, I., Tate, K., & Talbott, K. (2015). Organizational agility. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 31(2), 675–686.
- Hatzijordanou, N., Bohn, N., & Terzidis, O. (2019). A systematic literature review on competitor analysis: Status quo and start-up specifics. *Management Review Quarterly*, 69(4), 415–458.
- Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., Camp, S. M., & Sexton, D. L. (2001). Strategic entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurial strategies for wealth creation. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(6–7), 479–491.
- Hmieleski, K. M., & Corbett, A. C. (2006). Proclivity for improvisation as a predictor of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 44(1), 45–63.

- Houghton, J. D., Neck, C. P., & Manz, C. C. (2004). Self-leadership and superleadership. In C. L. Pearce & J. A. Conger (Eds.), *Shared leadership: Reframing the hows and whys of leadership* (pp. 123–140). SAGE Publications.
- Hussain, M., Manzoor, S. R., Shamsurrehman, S. R. A., & Zia-Ud-Din, I. (2011). Relationship of celebrity endorsement with consumers impulse buying in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research in Business*, 1(10), 67-72.
- Ireland, R. D., Hitt, M. A., & Sirmon, D. G. (2003). A model of strategic entrepreneurship: The construct and its dimensions. *Journal of Management*, 29(6), 963–989.
- Imran, M., Liu, X., Arif, M., Rahman, S. U., Manan, F., Khattak, S. R., & Wang, R. (2023). Sustainable corporate governance mediates between firm performance and corporate social responsibility using structural equation modelling. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 11, 1121853.
- Kamoche, K., & Cunha, M. P. E. (2001). Minimal structures: From jazz improvisation to product innovation. *Organization Studies*, 22(5), 733–764.
- Khattak, S. R., Zada, M., Nouman, M., Rahman, S. U., Fayaz, M., Ullah, R., ... & Contreras-Barraza, N. (2022). Investigating inclusive leadership and pro-social rule breaking in hospitality industry: Important role of psychological safety and leadership identification. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(14), 8291.
- Ketchen Jr, D. J., Ireland, R. D., & Snow, C. C. (2007). Strategic entrepreneurship, collaborative innovation, and wealth creation. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 1(3–4), 371–385.
- Khan, A. A. (2020). Marketing agility and firm performance: A contingency perspective. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 12(4), 1–13.

- Lee, O. K., Sambamurthy, V., Lim, K. H., & Wei, K. K. (2015). How does IT ambidexterity impact organizational agility? *Information Systems Research*, 26(2), 398–417.
- Leybourne, S. A. (2006). Improvisation within management: Promoting flexibility and creativity in project management. *Management Decision*, 44(7), 983–995.
- Liu, H., Ke, W., Wei, K. K., & Lu, Y. (2016). The effects of social capital on firm substantive and symbolic performance: In the context of E-business. *Journal of Global Information Management*, 24(1), 61–85.
- Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G. (1996). Clarifying the entrepreneurial orientation construct and linking it to performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(1), 135–172.
- Mazzei, M. J., Ketchen, D. J., & Shook, C. L. (2017). Understanding strategic entrepreneurship: A “theoretical toolbox” approach. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 13, 631–663.
- Meinhardt, R., Junge, S., & Weiss, M. (2018). The organizational environment with its measures, antecedents, and consequences: A review and research agenda. *Management Review Quarterly*, 68, 195–235.
- Miller, D. (2011). Miller (1983) revisited: A reflection on EO research and some suggestions for the future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(5), 873–894.
- Miner, A. S., Bassof, P., & Moorman, C. (2001). Organizational improvisation and learning: A field study. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 46(2), 304–337.
- Moorman, C., & Miner, A. S. (1998). Organizational improvisation and organizational memory. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(4), 698–723.
- Moorman, C., & Miner, A. S. (1998). The convergence of planning and execution: Improvisation in new product development. *Journal of Marketing*, 62(3), 1–20.

- Morris, M. H., Kuratko, D. F., & Covin, J. G. (2008). *Corporate entrepreneurship and innovation* (2nd ed.). Thomson Higher Education.
- Nejatian, H., Zarei, M. H., Nejati, M., & Amiri, A. N. (2018). A hybrid strategic model of organizational agility. *International Journal of Agile Systems and Management*, 11(4), 285–308.
- Nelson, R. R., & Harvey, F. (1995). The diffusion of innovations in dynamic networks: An agent-based computational approach. *Computational & Mathematical Organization Theory*, 1(4), 295–312.
- Orlikowski, W. J. (1996). Improvising organizational transformation over time: A situated change perspective. *Information Systems Research*, 7(1), 63–92.
- Park, Y. (2011). The dynamics of opportunity and threat management in turbulent markets: The role of sensing, seizing, and transforming. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(18), 33–44.
- Patil, S. K., & Suresh, M. (2019). A literature review on workforce agility. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 51(1), 19–30.
- Pavlou, P. A., & El Sawy, O. A. (2010). The "third hand": IT-enabled competitive advantage in turbulence through improvisational capabilities. *Information Systems Research*, 21(3), 443–471.
- Poolton, J., & Ismail, H. (2000). New developments in innovation. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 15(8), 795–811.
- Rehman, S. U., Ullah, R., Imran, M., Iqbal, K., Saleem, Z., & Khattak, S. R. (2021). Intolerance of uncertainty and mental well-being: Important role of loneliness and fear of COVID-19: Evidence from Higher Educational Institutions. *Multicult. Educ*, 7(1), 147-54.
- Rhee, J., Park, T., & Lee, D. H. (2010). Drivers of innovativeness and performance for innovative SMEs in South Korea: Mediation of learning orientation. *Technovation*, 30(1), 65–75.

- Robson, C. (2011). *Real world research: A resource for social-scientists and practitioner-researchers* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research methods for business students*. Pearson Education.
- Schuh, G., Prote, J. P., Gützlaff, A., Ays, J., & Donner, J. (2019). Managing production agility in the era of Industry 4.0. *Procedia CIRP*, 81, 736–741.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1942). *Capitalism, socialism and democracy*. Harper & Brothers.
- Shane, S., & Venkataraman, S. (2000). The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), 217–226.
- Sherehiy, B. (2008). A model of agility transformation: Review and synthesis. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 38(11–12), 1039–1050.
- Sherehiy, B. (2008). *Relationships between agility strategy, work organization and workforce agility*. University of Louisville.
- Sherehiy, B., Karwowski, W., & Layer, J. K. (2007). A review of enterprise agility: Concepts, frameworks, and attributes. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 37(5), 445–460.
- Simsek, Z., Heavey, C., & Fox, B. C. (2017). (Meta-) Framing strategic entrepreneurship. *Strategic Organization*, 15(4), 504–518.
- Siren, C. A., Kohtamäki, M., & Kuckertz, A. (2012). Exploration and exploitation strategies, profit performance, and the mediating role of strategic learning: Escaping the exploitation trap. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 6(1), 18–41.
- Smircich, L., & Stubbart, C. (1985). Strategic management in an enacted world. *Academy of Management Review*, 10(4), 724–736.
- Teece, D. J. (2007). Explicating dynamic capabilities: The nature and microfoundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319–1350.

- Teece, D. J. (2012). Dynamic capabilities: Routines versus entrepreneurial action. *Journal of Management Studies*, 49(8), 1395–1401.
- Thomas, J. B., Clark, S. M., & Gioia, D. A. (1993). Strategic sensemaking and organizational performance: Linkages among scanning, interpretation, action, and outcomes. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(2), 239–270.
- Tsourveloudis, N. C., & Valavanis, K. P. (2002). On the measurement of enterprise agility. *Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems*, 33(3), 329–342.
- Ullah, R., & Khattak, S. R. (2018). The Buffering Effect of Teamwork Effectiveness on the Relationship between Employee Work Engagement and Behavioral Outcomes. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, 12(1).
- Vera, D., & Crossan, M. (2005). Improvisation and innovative performance in teams. *Organization Science*, 16(3), 203–224.
- Vinodh, S. (2010). Improvement of agility and sustainability: A case study in an Indian rotary switches manufacturing organisation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 18(10–11), 1015–1020.
- Vinodh, S., Aravindraj, S., Pushkar, B., & Kishore, S. (2012). Estimation of reliability and validity of agility constructs using structural equation modelling. *International Journal of Production Research*, 50(23), 6737–6745.
- Vinodh, S., Devadasan, S. R., Vasudeva Reddy, B., & Radicand, K. (2010). Agility index measurement using multi-grade fuzzy approach integrated in a 20 criteria agile model. *International Journal of Production Research*, 48(23), 7159–7176.
- Webb, J. W., Ketchen Jr, D. J., & Ireland, R. D. (2010). Strategic entrepreneurship within family-controlled firms: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 1(2), 67–77.

- Wiklund, J., & Shepherd, D. (2005). Entrepreneurial orientation and small business performance: A configurational approach. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 20(1), 71–91.
- Winter, S. G. (2003). Understanding dynamic capabilities. *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(10), 991–995.
- Yang, C., & Liu, H. M. (2012). Boosting firm performance via enterprise agility and network structure. *Management Decision*, 50(6), 1022–1044.
- Yusuf, Y., Sarhadi, M., & Gunasekaran, A. (1999). Agile manufacturing: The drivers, concepts, and attributes. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62(1–2), 33–43.
- Yusuf, Y. Y., Sarhadi, M., & Gunasekaran, A. (1999). Agile manufacturing: The drivers, concepts and attributes. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62(1–2), 33–43.
- Zainal, H., Ibrahim, A., Yusof, N., & Zainuddin, M. (2020). The relationship between agile capabilities and performance: A study on Malaysian service firms. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(12), 735–745.
- Zhang, Z., & Sharifi, H. (2000). A methodology for achieving agility in manufacturing organisations: An introduction. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62(1–2), 7–22.